

MODELLING OF PEROVSKITE ON CRYSTALLINE SILICON TANDEM SOLAR CELL

Nigar Fatma

M.Tech, Student,

Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering
Al-Falah University, Dhauj, Faridabad, Haryana

Prof. Ravinder Kumar

Assistant professor,

Department of Electronics & Communication Engineering
Al-Falah University, Dhauj, Faridabad, Haryana

ABSTRACT

In the last few year, the photovoltaic solar cell has attracted a great deal of interest among researcher in the world. Because, development of new technologies for solar cell with enhanced efficiency is really a big challenge. With this perspective ,organic photovoltaic is considered an emerging photovoltaic technology with promising properties such as low cost flexibility ,light weight And large area manufacturing compatibility. But, stability of such cell is very less. An effective way to improve solar cell efficiency is to use a tandem structure where border part of spectrum of solar radiation is used and the thermalization loss of photon energy is minimized . To use solar radiation more effectively ,stack of multiple photo active layers with complementary absorption spectra in series is used to make a Tandem Solar Cell. This also has prospect of enhancing stability of organic solar cell. My objective is to develop a model of tandem solar cell: Organic-inorganic ,Perovskite On Crystalline Silicon(c-Si).

This research aims to study the perovskite solar cell using Methyl ammonium lead iodide as active material and the material of such perovskite. The study suggested that perovskite solar cell has superior performance. The simulation of a conventional P-N junction solar cell and perovskite cell has been done and verified with the experimental result available in literature. The proposed design composed of perovskite cell as top sub cell and c-Si as bottom sub-cell with silicon based tunnel junction that provides majority carrier recombination between sub cells. As this design is a combination of high and low band gap materials, it overcomes the problem of poor use of solar easier and cheaper which reduces the overall cost. A theoretical model of perovskite on c-si solar cell has been developed. Performance of the proposed solar cell has been studied by varying device parameter , e.g. thickness of different layers and results have been analyzed. Finally, this thesis has been concluded with the future scope of work.

Key words: Perovskite, solar cell, Crystalline Silicon, P-N junction, Organic-inorganic

INTRODUCTION

Developing alternative energy resources with high efficiency and low emission has become of great importance with increasing concerns about fossil fuel insufficiency, high oil prices, global warming, and damage to environment and ecosystem. In this concern, photovoltaic solar energy is a clean, renewable,

energy with a long service life and high reliability. A photovoltaic system converts sunlight into electricity. The basic device of a photovoltaic system is the photovoltaic cell commercially known as Solar Cell. Cells may be grouped to form panels or modules. The modeling and simulation of photovoltaics (PV) have made a great transition and form an important part of power generation in this present age. However, large-scale implementation of solar energy is not economically feasible because of its high cost as compared to the traditional power sources. The effort to improve the efficiency of solar cell and reduce their costs has been a major concern for a long time. The photovoltaic community has demonstrated and proposed a wide variety of solar cell structures using a wide range of photovoltaic materials and on the basis of used materials for solar cell fabrication, solar cell has categorized into different generations. In this chapter, a brief historical background with different generations of solar cell has been described.

AIM OF THE STUDY

In order to ensure the extensive use of solar cell, cost of the device must be significantly low. Several researchers have been working either on the aspect of cost reduction or efficiency enhancement. Because, development of new technologies for solar cell with enhanced efficiency is really a big challenge. In last section, we have given a brief idea about different types of solar cell with their advantages and their limitations. There are many new approaches: Multijunction solar cell, Heterojunction solar cell, Tandem structure solar cell are used to increase the absorption for better utilization of solar spectrum. This thesis aims to propose a model of a solar cell using organometallic material to enhance the efficiency, reduce the cost per watt and also to enhance the stability of organic solar cell.

PEROVSKITE SOLAR CELL

The perovskite materials have been well known for many years, but the first incorporation into a solar cell was reported by Miyasaka et al. in 2009.^[21] This was based on a dye-sensitized solar cell architecture, and generated only 3.8% power conversion efficiency (PCE) with a thin layer of perovskite on mesoporous TiO₂ as electron-collector. Moreover, because a liquid corrosive electrolyte was used, the cell was only stable for a matter of minutes. Park et al. improved upon this in 2011, using the same dye-sensitized concept, achieving 6.5% PCE.^[43]

A breakthrough came in 2012, when Henry Snaith and Mike Lee from the University of Oxford realised that the perovskite was stable if contacted with a solid-state hole transporter such as *spiro-OMeTAD* and did not require the mesoporous TiO₂ layer in order to transport electrons.^{[44][45]} They showed that efficiencies of almost 10% were achievable using the '*sensitized*' TiO₂ architecture with the solid-state hole transporter, but higher efficiencies, above 10%, were attained by replacing it with an inert scaffold. Further experiments in replacing the mesoporous TiO₂ with Al₂O₃ resulted in increased open-circuit voltage and a relative improvement in efficiency of 3–5% more than those with TiO₂ scaffolds.^[23] This led to the hypothesis that a scaffold is not needed for electron extraction, which was later proved correct.

In 2013 both the planar and sensitized architectures saw a number of developments. Burschka et al. demonstrated a deposition technique for the sensitized architecture exceeding 15% efficiency by a two-step solution processing, and at a similar time Liu et al. showed that it was possible to fabricate planar solar cells by thermal evaporation, also achieving more than 15% efficiency. Docampo et al. also showed that it was possible to fabricate perovskite solar cells in the typical 'organic solar cell' architecture, an 'inverted' configuration with the hole transporter below and the electron collector above the perovskite planar film.

A range of new deposition techniques and even higher efficiencies were reported in 2014. A reverse-scan efficiency of 19.3% was claimed by Yang Yang at UCLA using the planar thin-film architecture. In November 2014, a device by researchers from KRICT achieved a record with the certification of a non-stabilized efficiency of 20.1%.^[3] In December 2015, a new record efficiency of 21.0% was achieved by researchers at EPFL.^[3] As of March 2016, researchers from KRICT and UNIST hold the highest certified record for a single-junction perovskite solar cell with 22.1%.^[3]

In the last two years, many different configurations have been analyzed varying cell configuration, selective contacts, and even the kind of perovskite utilized [1,2]. Despite this broad range of variations, probably the most extensively studied has been the $CH_3NH_3PbI_3$ perovskite and its other analogous with Cl and Br as absorber materials, in combination with TiO_2 or ZnO as electron transport material (ETM) and with proper hole transport material e.g. *spiro-OMeTad*, Cu_2O , CuI etc.

Schematic of Perovskite Solar Cell

The perovskite-based solar cells commonly incorporated the perovskite as the absorbing layer between an n-type electron-transporting layer such as TiO_2 , ZnO and a p-type hole-transporting layer such as Cu_2O , CuI , or any other suitable material have demonstrated high efficiency. Research result has shown that the perovskites have good charge (electron or hole) transport properties, resulting in high efficiencies of the solar cells.

Figure 1 Structure of a Planar Heterojunction Perovskite Solar Cell

Researchers have produced perovskite solar cell using different device structure. These show the possible ways that have been recently used in the design and fabrication of perovskite solar cell devices with different performance. A theoretical study of perovskite cell based on the structure shown in Fig. 3.3 their simulation using MATLAB R2009a has been done in this thesis. This is a planar heterojunction perovskite solar cell which is popularly used in perovskite solar cell devices. In this structure the transparent conducting oxide (TCO) is deposited on a glass substrate, perovskite (MAPbI_3) is sandwiched between ETM and HTM and a cathode (Au) layer which serve as the electrodes.

TANDEM SOLAR CELL

A single junction solar cell makes poor use of the solar spectrum for two reasons; first, photons with energies less than the bandgap do not contribute at all. Second, each photon with higher energy contributes one electron to the current; however, all the energy exceeding the bandgap is lost. For a better use of the photon energies we are modeling a structure in which different semiconductor materials are used and guide each photon into an absorber where the bandgap matches the photon energy.

The simplest structure of this kind is the tandem where two absorbers are stacked making Top Cell and Bottom Cell. For the combination of a high and a low bandgap material the illumination should first strike the absorber with the high bandgap because there light with high energy will be absorbed with a high output voltage. Furthermore, this material will be transparent for low energy light which can be passed on to the second absorber with the lower bandgap. Thus, high bandgap absorbing material should be used for top cell and lower bandgap for bottom cell. In this way, the Tandem fabrication techniques improve the performance of existing designs. In the following section, we have described the model and carrier dynamics of proposed design.

MODEL DESCRIPTION

A design layout of Perovskite on *c-Si* cell has shown in Fig. 2. In this structure, the Perovskite $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ is used as active material in the top cell and the bottom cell is a *c-Si* cell which is mainly responsible for absorption. The continuity of current between these two cells will be established by a tunnel junction. The structure consists of a 50 nm thick *ZnO* electron transport material (ETM), $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ absorbing layer of various thickness, and a 850 nm thick hole transport material (HTM) layer. The tunnel junction of highly doped *Si* (*p++*)/*Si* (*n++*) each of thickness 20 nm insures the electrical connection between the two subcells. A *p*-type *Si* wafer substrate with acceptor doping 10^{16} cm^{-3} with thickness as a variable parameter. Finally, a 100 nm thick *p+* *Si* layer with acceptor doping 10^{19} cm^{-3} is used for the back contact. At the top of the structure, a transparent conducting oxide (TCO), ITO, is layered which provides electrical contact as well as antireflecting coating, so, light can incident through this layer. The key parameters taken from the literature which are used in our simulations for the *ZnO*, $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ Perovskite .

Figure 2: Schematic Tandem Structure for Perovskite on c-Si

When light is incident on the device, electron-hole pairs (EHPs) are generated mainly within the active layer. Now the photogenerated electrons and holes are separated out by drift and diffusion [sir] process giving rise to the photocurrent and Si materials are summarized in Table I.

Table 1: Parameters Values for $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$, ZnO, Si

Parameters	$\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$	ZnO	Si
Doping Concentration (/m ³)	10^{21}	10^{26}	$N_A = 10^{18}$ $N_D = 10^{24}$
Intrinsic Carrier Concentration(/m ³)	$4 \cdot 10^{12}$	$1 \cdot 10^{12}$	$1.5 \cdot 10^{10}$
Hole mobility (μ_p , m ² /V.s)	$90 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$5-50 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$500 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Electron mobility (μ_n , m ² /V.s)	$178 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$200 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1300 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Hole Life time (τ_p , s)	$187 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$2.8 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10^{-3}
Electron Life time (τ_n , s)	$330 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10^{-9}	10^{-3}
Eg (eV)	1.55	3.37	1.1
χ (eV)	4.1	4.29	4.05
ϵ_r	9	8.12	11.8
Electron effective mass	$0.197m_0$	$0.318m_0$	-
Hole effective mass	$0.34 m_0$	$0.5m_0$	-
Surface Recombination Velocity (m/s)	~ 10	$1.5 \cdot 10^3$	10^3

PHOTOCURRENT AND EFFICIENCY OF PROPOSED DESIGN

Photocurrent is the first step to find the characteristics of a solar cell. It defines its behavior with voltage ($J-V$ plot). For this, calculation of photocurrent of top cell (Perovskite cell) and bottom cell (c-Si) considering the effect of each layer for allowing the solar irradiance to next layer by using optical modeling has been done. First of all, photocurrent of conventional homojunction silicon solar cell has been done. Then on the basis of this concept, photocurrent for heterojunction perovskite cell has been calculated and then calculation for photocurrent of tandem structure has been done. All these have been described in next sections.

Photocurrent calculation for c-Si solar cell

In this section we derive the photocurrent for a silicon p-n junction solar cell which serves as a reference device for all solar cells. The photocurrent calculation for perovskites top sub-cell will be based on this concept. A schematic representative of a solar cell is shown in Fig. 3. It consists of a shallow p-n junction (homojunction) formed on the p-Si wafer. Photogenerated electrons and holes are separated out by drift and diffusion process giving rise to the photocurrent. When cell is under illumination, the generation rate of electron-hole pairs at a distance x from the semiconductor surface is given by

$$G(\lambda, x) = \alpha(\lambda) \phi(\lambda) [1 - R(\lambda)] \exp[-\alpha(\lambda) x] \quad (4.1)$$

Where, $\alpha(\lambda)$ = Absorption Coefficient

$\phi(\lambda)$ = No. of incident photons per area per time per unit bandwidth
Reflection Coefficient (the fraction of photons reflected from

$R(\lambda)$ =
front surface)

These parameters are wavelength dependent.

For our calculation, we assume an abrupt junction with constant doping on each side. Here $N_D \gg N_A$, so the depletion region at the n-side can be neglected. There are no electric fields outside the depletion region. Photogenerated carriers in outside the depletion regions are collected by a diffusion process while that in the depletion region by drift process. We divide the collection of photogenerated carriers in three regions: the top neutral region, the depletion region of the junction, and the substrate neutral region.

Figure: 3 Schematic of a p-n homojunction solar cell and Energy band diagram

Here W_D is the depletion region in p-side and due to high doping in n-side depletion region of n-side is neglected. The co-ordinate has started from n^+ layer.

So, from figure, Thickness of emitter, $t_{\text{emitter}} \sim x_j$

Thickness of absorber layer, $t_{\text{absorber}} \sim (H - x_j) = (H' + W_D)$

Under low-injection condition, the one-dimensional, steady-state continuity equations for electrons in the p-type substrate is

$$G_n - \left(\frac{n_p - n_{p0}}{\tau_n} \right) + \frac{1}{q} \frac{dJ_n}{dx} = 0 \quad (4.2)$$

and the same for hole in the n-type layer is

$$G_p - \left(\frac{p_n - p_{n0}}{\tau_p} \right) - \frac{1}{q} \frac{dJ_p}{dx} = 0 \quad (4.3)$$

Now, the current density equation for electrons and holes are

$$J_n = q\mu_n n_p \mathcal{E} + qD_n \left(\frac{dn_p}{dx} \right) \quad (4.4)$$

$$J_p = q\mu_p p_n \varepsilon - qD_p \left(\frac{dp_n}{dx} \right) \quad (4.5)$$

where, G is the generation rate, J is the conduction current density, τ is minority carrier life time and D is the diffusion co-efficient. Suffices n and p are respectively for electrons and holes. $n_{p0}(p_{n0})$ and $n_p(p_n)$ are density of electrons (holes) at equilibrium and under illumination respectively. For the top n -side of the junction, to obtain an expression for minority holes density as

$$D_p \frac{d^2 p_n}{dx^2} + \alpha \phi (1 - R) \exp(-\alpha x) - \left(\frac{p_n - p_{n0}}{\tau_p} \right) = 0 \quad (4.6)$$

The general solution to this equation is

$$p_n - p_{n0} = C_1 \cosh\left(\frac{x}{L_p}\right) + C_2 \sinh\left(\frac{x}{L_p}\right) - \frac{\alpha \phi (1 - R) \tau_p}{\alpha^2 L_p^2 - 1} \exp(-\alpha x) \quad (4.7)$$

where, $L_p = \sqrt{D_p \tau_p}$ is the diffusion length of minority holes, and C_1 and C_2 are constants.

To solve this equation, apply boundary conditions:

At $x = 0$,

$$D_p \frac{d(p_n - p_{n0})}{dx} = S_p (p_n - p_{n0}) \quad (4.8)$$

where S_p is the surface recombination velocity of holes.

$$\text{At } x = x_j, \quad p_n - p_{n0} \approx 0 \quad (4.9)$$

This implies, at the depletion edge, the excess minority carrier density is small due to the electric field in the depletion region. The resulting hole photocurrent density at depletion edge is

$$J_p = -qD_p \left(\frac{dp_n}{dx} \right) \text{ at } x = x_j$$

$$J_p = [q\phi(1 - R) \alpha L_p / (\alpha^2 L_p^2 - 1)] \left[\frac{\left(\frac{S_p L_p}{D_p} + \alpha L_p \right) - \exp(-\alpha x_j) \left(\frac{S_p L_p}{D_p} \cosh \frac{x_j}{L_p} + \sinh \frac{x_j}{L_p} \right)}{\frac{S_p L_p}{D_p} \sinh \frac{x_j}{L_p} + \cosh \frac{x_j}{L_p}} - \alpha L_p \exp(-\alpha x_j) \right] \quad (4.10)$$

This photocurrent would be generated and collected at the front of n-p junction at a given wavelength. For electron photocurrent generated in the p-Si substrate of the cell, $n_p - n_{p0} \approx 0$, at $x = x_j + W_D$ (4.11)

$$S_n (n_p - n_{p0}) = -D_n \left(\frac{dn_p}{dx} \right) \text{ at } x = H \quad (4.12)$$

where W_D is the depletion width, H is the width of the entire cell. S_n is the back surface recombination velocity. Here this velocity is at the interface of p-Si wafer and p^+ Si. Hence electron photocurrent density collected at the depletion edge $x = x_j + W_D$ is

$$J_n = qD_n \left(\frac{dn_p}{dx} \right) = [q\phi (1 - R) \alpha L_n / (\alpha^2 L_n^2 - 1)] \exp(-\alpha[(x_j + W_D)]) \left[\alpha L_n \frac{\left(\frac{S_n L_n}{D_n} \right) [\cosh \frac{H'}{L_n} - \exp(-\alpha H')] + \sin \frac{H'}{L_n} + \alpha L_n \exp(-\alpha H')}{\left(\frac{S_n L_n}{D_n} \right) \sinh \frac{H'}{L_n} + \cosh \frac{H'}{L_n}} \right] \quad (4.13)$$

The photocurrent due to carrier generation within the depletion region is $J_{dr} = F_{\text{Exiton}} q \phi_{\text{top}} (1 - R) \exp(-\alpha_{ZnO} x_j) [1 - \exp(-\alpha W_D)]$ (4.14)

This current is maximum because the photogenerated carriers inside the depletion region are accelerated out of the depletion region before they recombine due the effect of high electric field. For this we have assumed that all the generated carriers are collected without any recombination.

The total photocurrent at a given wavelength is:

$$J_L(\lambda) = J_p(\lambda) + J_n(\lambda) + J_{dr}(\lambda) \quad (4.15)$$

J_p and J_n are diffusion current whereas J_{dr} is drift current. Total photocurrent density can be obtained by integrating $J_L(\lambda)$ over full range of solar spectrum.

$$J_{ph} = \int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} J_L(\lambda) \quad (4.16)$$

Total load current density is

$$J_{tot} = J_s \left[\exp \left(\frac{qV}{kT} \right) - 1 \right] - J_{ph} \quad (4.17)$$

Where, dark current density, *i.e.*, when there is no light illuminated on solar cell is expressed as

$$J_{dark} = J_S \left[\exp\left(\frac{qV}{kT}\right) - 1 \right] \quad (4.18)$$

J_S saturation current density when there is no illumination and it is expressed as

$$J_S = \left[\frac{qD_n n_i^2}{L_n N_A} + \frac{qD_p n_i^2}{L_p N_D} \right] \quad (4.19)$$

Now, we can obtain the *J-V* characteristics using Eq. (4.17). We can find other performance parameter like efficiency and fill-factor from that characteristic.

The spectral response is defined as:

$$SR(\lambda) = \frac{J_L(\lambda)}{q\phi(1-R)} \quad (4.20)$$

PHOTOCURRENT CALCULATION FOR PEROVSKITE CELL

In previous section we have studied a c-Si solar cell where a homojunction is formed between n-type and p-type Si interfaces. The junction can be heterojunction as made between *GaAs/Si* thin film solar cells. The band-gap energy of *GaAs* is 1.4 eV and that of *Si* is 1.1 eV. Due to the different band-gap energy of p-type and n-type material, the junction formed is heterojunction which add an extra effect carrier trapping at band offsets which reduces the efficiency of solar cell. This band offsets depends on carrier doping and band gap energy, *i.e.*, depends on device structure. In perovskite solar cell, the junction formed is heterojunction but, in our design there is no confinement or trapping of charge carriers. A schematic structure of stand-alone perovskites solar cell is shown in Fig. Here, the materials are chosen in such a way that the carriers should not confine. A heterojunction is formed between n-type ZnO and p-type CH₃NH₃PbI₃ with bandgap 3.2 eV and 1.55 eV respectively in perovskite cell. We solved the continuity equations and current density equations for both electrons and holes for heterojunctions using boundary conditions likewise in previous section. The photocurrent equation for hole in n-type ETM is expressed as

$$J_{p,top} = [q\phi(1-R)\alpha_1 L_p / (\alpha_1^2 L_p^2 - 1)] \left[\frac{\left(\frac{S_p L_p}{D_p} + \alpha_1 L_p\right) - \exp(-\alpha_1 x_j) \left(\frac{S_p L_p}{D_p} \cosh \frac{x_j}{L_p} + \sinh \frac{x_j}{L_p}\right)}{\frac{S_p L_p}{D_p} \sinh \frac{x_j}{L_p} + \cosh \frac{x_j}{L_p}} - \alpha_1 L_p \exp(-\alpha_1 x_j) \right] \quad (4.21)$$

The photocurrent equation for electron is expressed as

$$J_{n,top} = [q\phi (1 - R) \alpha_2 L_n / (\alpha^2 L_n^2 - 1)] \exp(-\alpha_2 W_D + \alpha_1 x_j) \left[\alpha_2 L_n - \frac{\left(\frac{S_n L_n}{D_n}\right) [\cosh \frac{H'}{L_n} - \exp(-\alpha_2 H')] + \sin \frac{H'}{L_n} + \alpha L_n \exp(-\alpha_2 H')}{\left(\frac{S_n L_n}{D_n}\right) \sinh \frac{H'}{L_n} + \cosh \frac{H'}{L_n}} \right] \quad (4.22)$$

The photocurrent due to carrier generation within the depletion region is $J_{dr} = q\phi (1 - R) \exp(-\alpha x_j) [1 - \exp(-\alpha W_D)]$ (4.23)

The total photocurrent at a given wavelength is :

$$J_L(\lambda) = J_p(\lambda) + J_n(\lambda) + J_{dr}(\lambda) \quad (4.24)$$

Total photocurrent density can be obtained by integrating $J_L(\lambda)$ over full range of solar spectrum.

$$J_{ph} = \int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} J_L(\lambda) \quad (4.25)$$

Total load current density is

$$J_{tot} = J_S \left[\exp\left(\frac{qV}{kT}\right) - 1 \right] - J_{ph} \quad (4.26)$$

Where, dark current density, *i.e.*, when there is no light illuminated on solar cell is expressed as

$$J_{dark} = J_S \left[\exp\left(\frac{qV}{kT}\right) - 1 \right] \quad (4.27)$$

J_S saturation current density for heterojunction when there is no illumination and it is expressed as

$$J_S = \left[\frac{qD_n n_{in}^2}{L_n N_A} + \frac{qD_p n_{ip}^2}{L_p N_D} \right] \quad (4.28)$$

Where n_{in} and n_{ip} are intrinsic carrier concentration of n-side and p-side respectively.

OPTICAL MODELING

The design proposed in this thesis is tandem structure consists of top cell and bottom cell. Due to this the amount of incident photon flux for each layer will be different. By using optical modeling for incident photon flux, it is possible to determine the incident spectrum on each subcell. Each layer of the tandem cell is described by a transfer matrix and transmittance coefficient for each layer is

$$T_M = \left(\frac{2 n_0}{|n_s M_{11} + n_0 n_s M_{12} + M_{21} + n_0 M_{22}|} \right)^2 \quad (4.29)$$

Here, n_0 and n_s are superstrate and substrate refractive indices respectively.

Where

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} \cos t \frac{2\pi \left(n - \frac{i\lambda\alpha}{4\pi}\right)}{\lambda} & i \frac{\sin t \frac{2\pi \left(n - \frac{i\lambda\alpha}{4\pi}\right)}{\lambda}}{\left(n - \frac{i\lambda\alpha}{4\pi}\right)} \\ i \left(n - \frac{i\lambda\alpha}{4\pi}\right) \sin t \frac{2\pi \left(n - \frac{i\lambda\alpha}{4\pi}\right)}{\lambda} & \cos t \frac{2\pi \left(n - \frac{i\lambda\alpha}{4\pi}\right)}{\lambda} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.30)$$

Here n and t are refractive index and the thickness of the layer respectively. α is the absorption coefficient of the layer and λ is the wavelength.

The incident photon flux on the top and bottom subcell is given by

$$\phi_{top} = T_{M,TCO} \times T_{M,ETM} \times \phi_{solar} \quad (4.31)$$

$$\phi_{bottom} = T_{M,perovskite} \times T_{M,TCO} \times T_{M,ETM} \times \phi_{solar} \quad (4.32)$$

Where, ϕ_{solar} is the incident photo flux on top of the TCO layer, $T_{M,TCO}$, $T_{M,ETM}$ and $T_{M,perovskite}$ are transmission coefficient of TCO, ETM layer and top cell respectively.

SIMULATION RESULT FOR PEROVSKITE SOLAR CELL

The photocurrent calculation for perovskite solar cell has been done using equations from (4.21) to (4.32). Photocurrent at particular wavelength is calculated using Eq. (4.24) and then by integrating using Eq. (4.25) over full spectrum of solar radiation under AM1.5 solar spectrum, total photocurrent is obtained. Now, the $J-V$ characteristic is plotted using equations from Eq. (4.26) to Eq. (4.32) and plot has shown in Fig. 4. The absorption coefficients of $CH_3NH_3PbI_3$ and ZnO used for simulation is shown in Fig. 5 are taken from literature [1]. The required parameters are given in Table I. The other constants which are used in photocurrent calculation are listed in Table II.

Efficiency calculation is very important for a solar cell. Efficiency of the perovskite solar cell for different thickness of perovskite absorber is determined by using the incident optical power under AM 1.5 solar spectrum and by using the extracted maximum area under $J-V$ plot. It is clear from $J-V$ plot shown in Fig. 5, the current density increases with increase in absorber thickness but there is a negligible change in open circuit voltage (V_{oc}). A Table III has shown for quick review.

Figure 4.: Absorption coefficients of MAPbI₃ and ZnO

Fig. 4 taken from literature [] shows the absorption coefficient of our required material c-Si and CH₃NH₃PbI₃ (MAPI₃). It represents that the absorption co-efficient of MAPbI₃ is higher in visible region (~ 350nm – 750nm) which is the highest flux density of solar spectrum. After visible region, in infrared region (IR), it is almost negligible. On the other hand, c- Si has lower absorption coefficient in visible region compare to MAPbI₃ but, it also absorbs photons in near infrared region (NIR). This variation is due to different band gap energy of MAPbI₃ and c-Si which are 1.55eV and 1.1eV respectively. As $E_g = h.c/\lambda$, higher bandgap energy will absorb lower wavelength and lower bandgap energy will absorb higher wavelength and hence, this is the case for MAPbI₃ and c-Si.

Table II: Value of constants used in simulation

Constants	Value
Electronic Charge (q)	1.6×10^{-19} C
Planck's Constant (h)	6.634×10^{-34}
Absolute Permittivity (ϵ)	8.854×10^{-12}
Boltzman's Constant (k)	1.3807×10^{-23}
Electronic mass (m_0)	9.1×10^{-31}

Figure 5: J - V plot of perovskite solar cell for different thickness of absorber

Figure 6: Perovskite cell efficiency (%) with thickness

Another plot has plotted the efficiency with thickness for different thickness of ETM which clearly shows that efficiency increases with thickness upto a particular thickness and then it becomes constant. This is mainly due to enhanced absorption of light with increased thickness. It absorbs more photons, hence more electron hole pairs generate and hence efficiency increases. But after a particular thickness, efficiency get saturated because of effect of diffusion length. With increase in thickness of cell, depletion region will also increase. If diffusion length of generated carriers within depletion region is less than the width of the depletion region, then they won't reach to their respective electrode.

Table III: Current Density (J_{sc}), Open Circuit Voltage (V_{oc}) and Efficiency (%) for different thickness of absorber

Thickness of absorber ($t_{\text{Perovskite}}$, nm)	J_{sc} (A/m ²)	V_{oc} (V)	Efficiency (%)
150	105.30	0.90	9.73
200	122.95	0.90	11.42
230	131.61	0.91	12.26
400	148.07	0.91	13.84

ENERGY BAND DIAGRAM OF PROPOSED DESIGN

Energy band diagram of proposed design at room temperature and thermal equilibrium has been developed with the help of *Anderson Model* and it has shown in Fig. 7. The energy-band model of an idealized anisotype abrupt Heterojunction was proposed by Anderson. We consider this model, since it can adequately explain most transport processes.

From energy band diagram, it was found that the energy difference between conduction band of electron transport layer ZnO and Perovskite $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ is very less which helps the electron to flow from device to front metal contact. The holes flow from device to back contact and recombine with the coming electrons. It is also found that the energy difference between E_c of p^{++} and n^{++} and E_v of p^{++} and n^{++} is very high and depletion region formed is very narrow through which electrons and holes tunnel between top cell and bottom cell which helps in the continuity of the current. The band gap energy and electron affinity of each layer has tabled in Table IV.

Fig 7: Energy Band Diagram for whole design

ZnO **Table IV:** Band gap energy and electron affinity of materials

Parameters	ZnO	Perovskite	Cu ₂ O	P ⁺⁺ Si	N ⁺⁺ Si	p	P ⁺
E _g	3.2	1.5	3.1	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.1
χ	4.2	4.1	2.1	4.05	4.05	4.05	4.05

OVERALL PHOTOCURRENT CALCULATION OF TANDEM CELL

Our tandem structure of solar cell consists of perovskite cell as top sub-cell and c-Si as bottom sub-cell. It behaves like two cell connected in series. So, their open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) is the sum of the voltages of sub-cells, while their short circuit current density (J_{sc}) is that of the subcells with the smallest current density. Hence the load current density for subcells can be obtained using equations from Eq. (4.10) to Eq. (4.32) as described in above sections. Open circuit voltage and short circuit current for each subcells can be obtained from the respective subcells J - V plot.

so,

$$V_{oc,overall} = V_{oc,top} + V_{oc,bottom}$$

$$J_{sc,overall} = \text{Min}(J_{sc,top}, J_{sc,bottom})$$

For a particular subcell, to calculate net current (load current) requires calculation of photocurrent density and dark current density. When the spectrum of sunlight strikes the front of the cell, due to the different materials used for subcells, some portions of the incoming spectrum is absorbed either fully or partly by the top subcells and rest is transmitted to the lower subcells. So, to calculate the photocurrent density of a subcell, it is required to determine the incident photon fluxes, on each of the subcells. Optical modeling using transfer matrix formulation is used to calculate the incident photon fluxes for each subcells which is described in section 4.3.3.

Simulation Results for overall Tandem Cell

The current density for each subcells have calculated using equations from Eq. (4.10) to Eq. (4.32). The simulation of perovskite cell to get J - V characteristics has done in section 4.3.4 and results are discussed. The overall current density ($J_{sc,overall}$) versus Voltage(V), J - V plot, for different top cell thickness with current matching is plotted and shown in Fig. 8 and 9, where the thickness of top cell emitter (ZnO) and bottom cell thickness is fixed at 50 nm and 20 μm is respectively. It has been seen that photocurrent density increases with increase in top cell thickness ($t_{top\ cell}$) like the stand alone perovskite solar cell. However, the current density is almost same as single perovskite cell but in tandem structure the overall open circuit voltage increases due to series combination of top cell and bottom cell and hence overall efficiency increases. From plot it is also clear that there is an increase in current density with increase in thickness of top cell ($t_{top\ cell}$) but open circuit voltage ($V_{oc,overall}$) is almost constant. For different thickness of top cell, the overall short circuit current ($J_{sc, overall}$), overall open circuit voltage ($V_{oc, overall}$) and efficiency has been summarized in Table V for quick reference. In Fig. 8, a plot has been shown where top cell current and bottom cell current density is different, i.e current matching is not achieved. As we have studied, in tandem solar cell, same current flow throughout the cell. So a good current matching is required between top cell and bottom cell.

Figure 8: J-V Plot for tandem cell (Overall cell) with top cell thickness of 230nm and bottom cell thickness of 20µm

Figure 9: J-V Plot for tandem cell (Overall cell) with top cell thickness of 300nm and bottom cell thickness of 60µm

Table VI:

$t_{\text{top cell}}$ (nm)	$t_{\text{bot cell}}$ (μm)	$J_{\text{sc,overall}}$ (A/m^2)	$V_{\text{oc,overall}}$ (V)	Overall Efficiency (%)	Matching Condition
230	20	131.61	1.52	21.68	Matched
300	60	148.07	1.53	24.39	
230	60	131.61	1.52	21.68	Unmatched
300	20	132.49	1.52	21.82	

Effect of Absorber Layer Thickness in Current Matching Issue

In this section, we first show that a good current matching between the Top and Bottom subcells is required to obtain a maximum efficiency of the tandem cell. It can be achieved with the help of absorbers thickness. We have calculated photocurrent of the top perovskite subcell, bottom silicon subcell individually in previous sections and the perovskites/Si tandem cell under AM 1.5 illumination. The doping level of the silicon tunnel junction is fixed to 10^{23} cm^{-3} and thickness is fixed at 20nm. For the silicon bottom cell, when absorber thickness is $20\mu\text{m}$, a short circuit current $J_{SC} = 150.34 \text{ A.cm}^{-2}$ and an open-circuit voltage $V_{OC} = 0.61 \text{ V}$ are obtained and lead to a cell efficiency of 8.34 %. The top cell gives $J_{SC} = 131.61 \text{ A.cm}^{-2}$, $V_{OC} = 0.91 \text{ V}$ and a cell efficiency of 12.26%. For the tandem cell, the open-circuit voltage is $V_{oc,overall} = 1.52 \text{ V}$, which corresponds to the sum of the open circuit voltages of each sub-cell. The short-circuit current is identical to that of the top cell, and corresponds to the maximum of the total current that can be reached in the tandem cell. When thickness of top subcell changes then it affects the bottom cell absorption and hence it affects the bottom cell current which may or may not equal to the top cell current. The overall current will be minimal of top cell and bottom cell current. A plot for unmatched condition is shown in Fig. 10. To get a better efficiency current should be matched. A plot overall efficiency ($\text{Eff}_{\text{overall}}$) Vs top cell thickness ($t_{\text{top cell}}$) has shown in Fig. 10 which describes the current matching point for different bottom cell thickness ($t_{\text{bot cell}}$). From this plot, it has been analyzed that overall efficiency increases with top cell thickness ($t_{\text{top cell}}$) upto current matching point. After this, efficiency becomes constant.

Fig 10: Current matching between the Top and Bottom subcells

Fig. 11: Efficiency of top cell with respect to top cell thickness

In Fig. 11, efficiency of top cell with respect to top cell thickness by keeping bottom cell thickness fixed and in Fig. 11, efficiency of bottom cell with respect to bottom cell thickness by keeping top cell thickness fixed has shown. From this plot, it has analyzed that with increase in $t_{top\ cell}$, top cell efficiency increases significantly because of increased absorption of photons, but, this is not the same for bottom cell. Bottom cell efficiency is almost constant with thickness. By keeping these in mind and with the help of Fig. 12, we have optimized some models for their respective fixed bottom cell thickness which is summarized in Table VII.

Table VII.: Models for their respective fixed bottom cell thickness

$t_{bot\ cell}$ (μm)	$t_{top\ cell}$ (nm)	$J_{sc,overall}$ (A/m^2)	$V_{oc,overall}$ (V)	Overall Efficiency (%)
20	230	131.61	1.52	21.68
40	288	145.55	1.52	23.98
60	300	148.07	1.53	24.39

Fig. 12: Efficiency of top cell with respect to top cell thickness

CONCLUSION

In this thesis, an attempt has been made for the design of a tandem structure solar cell: Perovskite on crystalline silicon(c-Si). The designed cell has two parts: top cell and bottom cell. The top cell has perovskite as active material while the bottom cell is c-Si cell. The main mechanism of current continuity through the top and bottom cell is tunneling. Energy band diagram of the design has been proposed through Anderson Model. The solar cell characteristics have been simulated using MATLAB *J-V* curve has plotted. Variation of efficiency with top cell thickness and bottom cell thickness has been studied. Thickness of c-Si plays an insignificant role in the variation of efficiency. Thickness of obtain optimized efficiency, because it has the main effect on overall cell. Keeping cost in mind, if we fix the thickness of bottom cell at 20 μm , then % efficiency is obtained with 230nm top cell thickness. Other combinations have also listed in Table VI. The maximum efficiency point shifts towards higher value of both thicknesses, but, it will increase the cost of the proposed design. At higher value of thickness, efficiency saturates. This is due to the fact that if carriers are produced outside the diffusion length, they cannot reach to the contact. Moreover, with increase in layer thickness material cost will increase which will increase the overall cost. Thus, in this thesis a theoretical and simulated on MATLAB model has been proposed

Future Work Scope

In this thesis, some parameters e.g, reflection coefficient has assumed constant which depends on wavelength, some parameters e.g, generation rate of EHPs which vary with distance and wavelength $G(\lambda, x)$ has considered only wavelength dependent. The work can be extend to study the effect of variation of these parameters.

The future scope of this project can be other developments include tuning perovskite properties with chemical compositions, developing efficient growth methods, optimizing hole transport materials, and engineering interface properties. In general, mixing halides in perovskite increases stability, diffusion length, improves mobility and reduces recombination rate. Hence, these properties can be added in design using mixed halide perovskites. In this thesis, current matching has done by varying thickness. In future, this can be done by band gap tuning of perovskite by using mixed halide perovskites.

In future, the efficiency can be further increased by using materials with high mobility as HTM. Optimization of the interfaces and selection of HTM and ETM may push forward the efficiencies to higher values. Incorporation of narrow band gap perovskites and plasmonic light harvester may broaden the spectral response with better light harvesting. Interface engineering and introduction of self-assembled layers will reduce losses and improve efficiency.

Although, the perovskite (MAPbI_3) based tandem cell has many advantages, but, there is an issue of using lead as it is toxic. This work can be move forward to replacement of lead with tin in perovskite ($\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{SnI}_3$) solar cell and may offer an environment friendly alternative.

REFERENCES

- 1) R.S.OhI,"Light sensitive electric device",US 2402662 A(1946)
- 2) APS News (American Physical society),"April @%,1954: Bell Labs Demonstrates the First Practical Silicon Solar Cell",18(4),(April 2009)
- 3) Tsokos,K.A,"Physics for the IB Diploma Full Colour", Cambridge University Press(2010).
- 4) J.Britt, C. Ferekides,"Thin-film CdS/CdTe solar cell with 15.8% efficiency", Appl.Phys.Lett.62:2851(1993).
- 5) Xuanzhi Wu,"High-efficiency polycrystalline CdTe thin-film solar cells",Solar Energy,77 (6):803-814(2004).
- 6) T.Tinoco, C. Rincon, M.Quintero and G.Sanchez Perez,"Phase Diagram and Optical Energy Gaps for $\text{CuInGa}_{1-y}\text{Se}_2$ Alloy",Physica status solidi(a) 124 (2):427(1991).
- 7) Stanbery,B.J."Copper Indium Selenides and Related Materials for Photovoltaic Devices",Critical Reviews in Solid State and Materials Science 27(2):73(2002).
- 8) Repins I , Contreras M.A, Egaas.B , DeHart. C,Scharf j,Perkins C.L,To.B and Noufi.R, "19.9% efficient $\text{ZnO/CdS/CuInGaSe}_2$ solar cell with 81.2% fill factor", Progress in Photovoltaics:Research and applications 16(3),235(2008).
- 9) Yablonovitch Eli,Miller Owen D,Kurtz S.R,"The Opto-Electronic Physics that Broke the Efficiency Limit in Solar Cells",38th IEEE photovoltaic Specialists Conference,001556(2012).
- 10) Pulfery, L.D., "Photovoltaic Power Generation",New York:Van Nostrand Reinhold Co.,(1978).
- 11) Nelson,jenny,"Polymer:fullerene bulk heterojunction solar cells", Materials Today 14(10):462-470(2011).
- 12) FooziehSohrabi,Ar ashNikniazi and HosseinMovla, "Optimization of Third Generation Nanostructured Silicon-Based Solar Cells",Solar Cells-Research and Application Perspective(2013).
- 13) M.H Liao,C.H.Chen,L.C.Chang,C. Yang, "A novel stress design for the type-2 heterojunction solar cell with superior performance ", Jnl.of Appl.Phys.,111,063109(2012).
- 14) Miles, R, "Photovoltaic solar cells: Choice of materials and production methods",80(10):1090-1097(2006).
- 15) New South Innovations,"New South Innovations News –UNSW breaks solar cell record", 2008-11-18.Archived from the original on April 25,2012.Retrieved 2012-06-23.
- 16) <http://cleantechnica.com/2012/05/31/sharp-hits-concentrator-solar-cell-efficiency-record-43-5/>
- 17) Kojima,Akihiro; Teshima, Kenjiro; Shirai, Yasuo; Miyasaka, Tsutomu, "Organometal Halide Perovskite as Visible-Light Sensitizers for Photovoltaic Cells", Journal of the American Chemical Society,131(17):6050-6051(2009).
- 18) <http://www.nrel.gov/ncpv/images/efficiency-chart.jpg>

- 19) Wei E.I. Sha, Xingang Ren, Luzhou Chen, and Wallace C.H Choy "The Efficiency Limit of CH₃NH₃PbI₃ Perovskite Solar Cells" Applied Physics Letters, 106 (22):221104,(2015).
- 20) Li, C. et al. Formability of ABX₃ (X=F, Cl, Br, I) halide perovskites. Acta Crystallogr. B 64, 702-707(2008).
- 21) McKinnon, N.K., Reeves, D.C. & Akabas, M. H. 5-HT₃ receptor ion size selectivity is property of the transmembrane channel, not the cytoplasmic vestibule portals. J. Gen. Physiol. 138, 453-466(2011).
- 22) Cohen, B. N., Labarca, C., Davidson, N. & Lester, H.A. Mutations in M2 alter the selectivity of mouse nicotinic acetylcholine receptor for organic and alkali metal cations. J. Gen. Physiol. 100, 373-400(1992).
- 23) Umari, P., Mosconi, E. & De Angelis, F. Relativistic GW calculations on CH₃NH₃PbI₃ and CH₃NH₃SnI₃ perovskites for solar cell applications. Sci. Rep. 4, 4467(2014).
- 24) G. Giorgi, J.I. Fujisawa, H. Segawa and K. Yamashita, J Phys Chem Lett, 4, 4213-4216(2013).
- 25) Bernabe Mari Soucase, Inmaculada Guita Pradas and Krishna R. Adhikari, "Perovskite Materials – Synthesis, Characterisation, Properties, and Applications-Numerical Simulations on Perovskite Photovoltaic Devices ", InTech(2016).
- 26) L. Etgar, P. Gao, Z. Xue, Q. Peng, A. K. Chandiran, B. Liu, M. K. Nazeeruddin and M. Graetzel, Journal of the American Chemical Society, 134, 17396-17399(2012)
- 27) W. Abu Laban and L. Etgar, Energy & Environmental Science, 6, 3249-3253(2013).
- 28) J. B. You, Z. R. Hong, Y. Yang, Q. Chen, M. Cai, T. B. Song, C. C. Chen, S. R. Lu, Y. S. Liu, H. P. Zhou and Y. Yang, Acs Nano, 8, 1674-1680(2014).
- 29) I. Grinberg, D. V. West, M. Torres, G. Y. Gou, D. M. Stein, L. Y. Wu, G. N. Chen, E. M. Gallo, A. Akbashev, P. K. Davies, J. E. Spanier and A. M. Rappe, Nature, 503, 509(2013).
- 30) K. T. B. Jarvist M. Frost, Federico Brivio, Christopher H. Hendon, Mark van Schilfgaarde, and Aron Walsh, Nano Lett, 14, 2584(2014).
- 31) Kojima A, Teshima K, Shirai Y, and Miyasaka, T, "Organometal halide perovskite as visible-light sensitizers for photovoltaic cells." J. Am. Chem. Soc. 131, 6050-6051 (2009).
- 32) Im, Jeong-Hyeok; Lee, Chang-Ryul; Lee, Jin-Wook; Park, Nam-Gyu "6.5% efficient perovskite quantum-dot-sensitized solar cell". Nanoscale 3 (10): 4088-93(2011).
- 33) Lee, M.M.; Teuscher, J.; Miyasaka, T.; Murakami, T.N.; Snaith, H.J., "Efficient Hybrid Solar Cells Based on Meso-Superstructured Organometal Halide Perovskites". Science 338(6107), 643-647(2012).
- 34) Hadlington, Simon, "perovskite coat gives hybrid solar cells a boost". RSC Chemistry world(2012).
- 35) Liu Mingzen, Johnston Michael B and Snaith Henry J, "Efficient planar heterojunction perovskite solar cells by vapour deposition". Nature 501(7467): 395-8(2013).

- 36) Burschka Julain, Pellet Norma, Moon Soo-Jin, Humphry-Baker Robin, Gao Peng, Nazeeruddin Mohammad K and Gratzel Michael, "Sequential deposition as a route to high-performance perovskite-sensitized solar-cells." *Nature* 499 (7458): 316-319, (2013).
- 37) Liu Mingzhen, Johnston Micheal B and Snaith Henry J, "Efficient planar heterojunction perovskite solar cells by vapour deposition". *Nature* 501 (7467): 395-398 (2013).
- 38) Mark Miodownik, "The perovskites light bulb moment for solar power", *The Guardian* (2014).
- 39) Docampo Pablo, Ball James M, Darwich Mariam, Eperon Giles E and Snaith Henry J, "Efficient organometal trihalide perovskite planar-heterojunction solar cells on flexible polymer substrates". *Nature communications* 4, (2013).
- 40) Zhou H, Chen Q, Li G, Luo S, Song T.-b, Duan H.-S., Hong Z, You J, Liu Y and Yang, Y, "Interface engineering of highly efficient perovskite solar cells". *Science* 345(6196): 542-546 (2014).
- 41) Soumyo Chatterjee and Amlan J. Pal, "Introducing Cu₂O Thin Films as a Hole Transport Layer in Efficient Planar Perovskite Solar Cell Structures", *J. Phys. Chem. C*, 120, 1428-1437 (2016).
- 42) S.M. Sze, "Semiconductor Devices Physics and Technology", Second Edition, John Wiley & Sons, INC. (2002).
- 43) Xie Ziang, Liu Shifeng, Qin Laixing, Pang Suping, Wang Wei, Yan Yu, Yao Li, Chen Zhijian, Wang Shufeng, Du Honglin, and G.G. Qin, "Refractive index and extinction coefficient of CH₃NH₃PbI₃ studied by spectroscopic ellipsometry", *Optical Material Express*, 5(1), 29-43 (2015).
- 44) Lili Yang, "Synthesis and characterization of ZnO nanostructures". Linköping Studies in Science and Technology, Dissertation No. 1327 (2010).
- 45) Ye Yang, Yong Yan, Mengjin Yang, Sukgeun Choi, Kai Zhu, Joseph M. Luther and Matthew C. Beard, "Low surface recombination velocity in solution-grown CH₃NH₃PbBr₃ perovskite single crystal", *Nature Communication*, 6:7961 (2015).